

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

**CURRENT PERSPECTIVES ON CLEANING VALIDATION IN
PHARMACEUTICAL INDUSTRY****P.Lingaeswara Rao^{1*}, Ch.V.Suresh², M.Sameera³, M.Ashok Kumar³, M.Sandhya Rani³,
Y. Srikrishna vara prasad³**¹Professor, Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Chennupati Indo American School of Pharmacy, Narasaraopet, Palnadu(Dt), Andhra Pradesh, pin:522601.²Principal, Department of Pharmaceutics, Chennupati Indo American School of Pharmacy, Narasaraopet, Palnadu(Dt), Andhra Pradesh, pin:522601.³Research Scholar, Department of Pharmaceutics, Chennupati Indo American School of Pharmacy, Narasaraopet, Palnadu(Dt), Andhra Pradesh, pin:522601.**Abstract:**

Pharmaceutical product and active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) can be contaminated by other pharmaceutical products or APIs, by cleaning agents, by microorganisms or by other materials e.g. air borne particles, dust, lubricants, raw materials, intermediates, etc. Cleaning procedure is the process of assuring that cleaning procedures effectively remove the potentially dangerous substances from equipments. This can be minimized by proper cleaning of equipment, apparatus as well as the processing area. So it is necessary to validate the cleaning procedures to ensure safety, efficacy, quality of the subsequent batches of drug product and regulatory requirements in Pharmaceutical product manufacture. It briefly provides an overview on mechanism of contamination, cleaning mechanisms, cleaning agents, procedure of cleaning, and sampling techniques. In pharmaceutical industry there are some possibilities of contamination and cross contamination because of improper cleaning of equipment, apparatus, processing area or the starting material, this can lead to severe hazards, therefore in pharmaceutical industry we can't afford any contamination as well as cross contamination. This can be minimized by proper cleaning of equipment, apparatus as well as the processing area. The Industry wants to achieve these main goals with the help of GMP. This review focused on the different types of cleaning process adapted by pharmaceutical industry, how the process of cleaning validation is done. In the cleaning validation different critical parameter, factor, material and critical process are monitored and validated so that the cleaning consistency can be achieved and documented accordingly.

Keywords: Contamination, clean in place, clean out of place, swab sampling

Corresponding author:**P.Lingaeswara Rao,**

Professor, Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis,

Chennupati Indo American School of Pharmacy,

Narasaraopet, Palnadu(Dt), Andhra Pradesh, pin:522601.

QR code

Please cite this article in press P.Lingaeswara Rao et al., *Current Perspectives On Cleaning Validation In Pharmaceutical Industry.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2025; 12 (02).

INTRODUCTION:

Cleaning validation is a documented process that proves the effectiveness and consistency in cleaning a pharmaceutical production equipment. Validations of equipment cleaning procedures are mainly used in pharmaceutical industries to prevent cross contamination and adulteration of drug products. The prime purpose of validating a cleaning process is to ensure compliance with federal and other standard regulations. The most important benefit of conducting such a validation work is the identification and correction of potential problems previously unsuspected, which could compromise the safety, efficacy or quality of subsequent batches of drug product produced within the equipment. Pharmaceutical products and active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) can be contaminated by other pharmaceutical products or APIs, by cleaning agents, by micro-organisms or by other material (e.g. airborne particles, dust, lubricants, raw materials, intermediates, auxiliaries). In many cases, the same equipment may be used for processing different products. To avoid contamination of the following pharmaceutical product, adequate cleaning procedures are essential. Cleaning procedures must strictly follow carefully established and validated methods of execution. This applies equally to the manufacture of pharmaceutical products and active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs). In any case, manufacturing processes have to be designed and carried out in a way that contamination is reduced to an acceptable level. Cleaning Validation is documented evidence that an approved cleaning procedure will provide equipment which is suitable for processing of pharmaceutical products or active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs).

Objective

The objectives of equipment cleaning and cleaning validation in an Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient (API) area are same as those in pharmaceutical production area. In both these areas efforts are necessary to prevent contamination of a future batch with the previous batch material.

The cleaning of 'difficult to reach' surface is one of the most important considerations in equipment cleaning validation. Equipment cleaning validation in an API facility is extremely important as cross contamination in one of the pharmaceutical dosage forms, will multiply the problem. Therefore, it is important to do a step-by-step evaluation of API process to determine the most practical and efficient way to monitor the effectiveness of the cleaning process. It is necessary to validate cleaning procedures for the following reasons.

1. It is a prime customer requirement since it ensures the purity and safety of the product.
2. It is a regulatory requirement in Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient product manufacture.
3. It also assures the quality of the process through an internal control and compliance.

Types of contaminations**1. Cross contamination with active ingredients**

Contamination of one batch of product with significant levels of residual active ingredients from a previous batch cannot be tolerated. In addition to the obvious problems posed by subjecting consumers or patients to unintended contaminants, potential clinically significant synergistic interactions between pharmacologically active chemicals are a real concern.

2. Contamination with unintended materials or compounds

While inert ingredients used in drug products are generally recognized as safe or have been shown to be safe for human consumption, the routine use, maintenance and cleaning of equipments provide the potential contamination with such items as equipment parts, lubricants, chemical cleaning agents and pieces of cleaning tools such as brushes and rags.

3. Microbiological contamination

Maintenance, cleaning and storage conditions may provide adventitious microorganisms with the opportunity to proliferate within the processing equipment.

General aspects of cleaning validation**Personnel**

Operators who perform cleaning routinely should be trained in the application of validated cleaning procedures. Training records should be available for all training carried out. It is difficult to validate a manual, i.e. an inherently variable/cleaning procedure. Therefore, operators carrying out manual cleaning procedures should be supervised at regular intervals.

Equipment

The design of the equipment should be carefully examined. Critical areas (those hardest to clean) should be identified, particularly in large systems that employ semi-automatic or fully automatic clean-in-place (CIP) systems. Dedicated equipment should be used for products which are difficult to remove (e.g. tarry or gummy residues in the bulk manufacturing), for equipment which is difficult to clean (e.g. bags for fluid bed dryers), or for products with a high safety risk (e.g. biologicals or products of high potency which may be difficult to detect below an acceptable limit).

Microbiological Aspects

The existence of conditions favourable to reproduction of microorganisms (e.g. moisture, temperature, crevices and rough surfaces) and the time of storage should be considered. The aim should be to prevent excessive microbial contamination. The period and when appropriate, conditions of storage of equipment before cleaning and the time between cleaning and equipment reuse, should form part of the validation of cleaning procedures. This is to provide confidence that routine cleaning and storage of equipment does not allow microbial proliferation.

Cleaning validation techniques for microorganisms

1. Swab Method
2. Surface Rinse Method
3. RODAC Plate Method
4. Limulus Amoebocyte Lysate Method
5. ATP Bioluminescence Method

1. Swab Method:

After cleaning the equipment, product contact surfaces could be swabbed to evaluate surface cleanliness. Swabs used should be compatible with the active ingredients and should not interfere with the assay. They should not cause any degradation of the compound. The solvent used for swabbing should provide good solubility for the compound and should not encourage degradation.

Advantages: Most common method used with selective media to isolate directly different microbial populations.

Disadvantages: Recovery may not be reproducible & quantitative.

2. Surface Rinse Method

Sampling and testing of rinse samples for residual active ingredient is a commonly adopted method to evaluate cleanliness. This is a convenient method in many cases and requires control over the solvent used for rinsing, the contact time and the mixing involved. The solvent used should be selected based on the solubility of the active ingredient and should either simulate a subsequent batch of product or at least provide adequate solubility.

Advantages: Higher counts obtained than swab method and better overall assessment possible.

Disadvantages: Entire surface evaluated, microbial population must be detached and membrane filtration necessary to obtain countable numbers.

3. Replicate Organism Direct Agar Contact Plate Method:

All samples will be collected on RODAC Plates. Surfaces, such as walls, floors, and ceilings should be dry and have been sanitized within twelve

hours of being sampled. Items such as cages and sipper tubes should be sampled close to five minutes after being disinfected. Two different techniques will be used for obtaining samples, depending on the sample site. These techniques include:

- **Flat Surfaces:** Gently press the rounded agar surface of the plate to the sample surface. Use a rolling motion, with a light uniform pressure, to ensure that the entire surface of the agar will contact the sample surface. Avoid pulling or sweeping the agar surface over the sample area, as this will destroy the agar surface, thereby rendering plate unusable.
- **Irregular Surfaces:** A sterile, cotton-tipped swab is moistened with sterile water and swabbed over such surfaces and into the corners of equipment. In the case of sipper tubes, the swab should be passed into and out of the tube three times. For other irregular surfaces, the swab should be rubbed over a surface area roughly the same size as the base of the RODAC Plate three times in an opposite direction between each successive stroke. Following sampling, the swab head should be gently rotated over the surface of the agar three times, again rolling in opposite direction between each successive stroke.

The RODAC Plates are placed upside down in the incubator located in the lab. The incubator should always be set on 36.7°C. After a 24 hour period, the plates are observed for growth. After 48 hours, the plates are removed from the incubator and the colonies counted using the electronic colony counter pen. After results are recorded, the plates are placed in a Bio-Hazard bag and disposed.

Results – The following system will be used to rate the results:

- 0-5 colonies: None or Very slight colonies (considered excellent)
- 6-15 colonies: Slight (considered good)
- 16-30 colonies: Moderate (borderline acceptable)
- 31-50 colonies: Significant (poor)
- >50 colonies: Heavy (unacceptable)

Advantages: Direct growth on media in contact plate is convenient, neutralizers may be included in media & different media may be used.

Disadvantages: Only applicable to surfaces that are smooth & have low counts.

4. Limulus Amoebocyte Lysate Method

This technique was widely used in the biopharmaceutical industry. The LAL test is performed by adding aliquots of sample or test materials to small quantities of a lysate preparation, followed by incubation at 37°C for 1 hour. The presence of endotoxins causes gel formation of the lysate material.

Advantages: Rapid, sensitive, quantitative measure of bacterial endotoxin levels.

Disadvantages: Indirect measurement of high numbers of gram-negative bacteria only.

5.ATP Bioluminescence Method

This type of analysis usually uses ATP-bioluminescence. The bioluminescence technique is an increasingly important alternative to classical microbiological methods. A defined surface area is wiped with a special swab and in the presence of magnesium ions, The extracted ATP is converted into light by means of a luciferin-luciferase enzymatic system. The result is available within a few minutes.

Advantages: Rapid, highly accurate & reliable method.

Disadvantages: Suitable for microbial counts in the range of 10^4 to 10^8 organisms as insufficiently sensitive for low microbial counts.

Cleaning validation techniques for contaminants or previous product residues

1. Swab method
2. Rinse solvent method
3. Conductivity testing
4. Placebo method

1.Swab method

Swabbing is commonly used to sample the surface of cleaned materials. The swab is then placed in a sample vial and sent to the Quality Control lab for analysis. Proper analytical technique is essential in order to evaluate the effectiveness of cleaning techniques.

2. Rinse method

Analysis of rinse water for residual cleaning agents or process materials is an essential component of cleaning validation. Insuring that the sample is not contaminated requires vigilance and properly following the relevant SOP's.

3. Conductivity method

The variation in conductivity of rinsed solvent indicates the cleaning efficiency. This method commonly employed for reactors, centrifuges and piping between large equipments.

4.Placebo method

Placebo is an inert material in which contaminants are dissolved or dispersed. Placebo method should be used in conjugation with Rinse or Swab method. Assurance found to be less when compared to other methods. It is not suitable for contaminants having higher particle size.

Detergents

The efficiency of cleaning procedures for the removal of detergent residues should be evaluated. Acceptable

limits should be defined for levels of detergent after cleaning. Ideally, there should be no residues detected. The possibility of detergent breakdown should be considered when validating cleaning procedures.

Detergents selection

Detergent should be easily removable.

The composition of the detergent should be known.

The possibility of detergent breakdown and detergent removal should be demonstrated.

Acceptable limits should be defined for detergent residues after cleaning.

Analytical Methods

The analytical methods should be validated before the Cleaning Validation Study is carried out.

The analytical methods used to detect residuals or contaminants should be specific for the substance to be assayed and provide a sensitivity that reflects the level of cleanliness determined to be acceptable by the company.

The analytical methods should be challenged in combination with the sampling methods used, to show that the contaminants can be recovered from the equipment surface and to show the level of recovery as well as the consistency of recovery.

Analysis of cleaning validation samples

There are many analytical techniques available that can be used in cleaning validation. But choosing the appropriate analytical tool depends on a variety of factors. The most important factor is to determine the specifications or parameters to be measured. The limit should always be established prior to the selection of the analytical tool.

1. Analysis of anionic and cationic surfactants is done by HPLC and Capillary electrophoresis (CE), where as amphoteric surfactants are analysed by HPLC and Evaporate light scattering detector.

2. Capillary electrophoresis can be used for many different types of analysis, viz; separation, detection and determination of sodium lauryl sulphate in cationic, anionic and non-ionic surfactant.

3. Micellar electro kinetic capillary chromatography is used for the separation of non-ionic alkyl phenol polyoxyethylene type surfactants.

4. Total organic carbon is used for the analysis of detergents, endotoxins, biological media and poly ethylene glycol.

5. Ion chromatography can be used for the analysis of inorganic, organic and surfactants present in the cleaners.

6. Thin layer chromatography is widely used for the qualitative determination of surfactants.

7. Atomic absorption spectroscopy is used for the determination of inorganic contaminants.

8. Portable mass spectrometer can be used to detect ultra sensitive measurements and identification of the residue.

Acceptance criteria

Carry-over of product residues should meet defined criteria, for example the most stringent of the following three criteria:

Chemical

(a) No more than 0.1% of the normal therapeutic dose of any product will appear in the maximum daily dose of the following product,

(b) No more than 10 ppm of any product will appear in another product,

Visual

No quantity of residue should be visible on the equipment after cleaning procedures are performed.

(a) No quantity of residue should be visible on the equipment after cleaning procedures are performed. Spiking studies should determine the concentration at which most active ingredients are visible,

(b) For certain allergenic ingredients, penicillins, cephalosporins or potent steroids and cytotoxics, the limit should be below the limit of detection by best available analytical methods.

Microbiological limit

Total aerobic microbial count - NMT
1000 cfu/g

Total combined Yeast and mold count - NMT
100 cfu/g

Absence of USP indicator organisms i.e. - E.coli
- S. aureus
- Salmonella species

Current approaches in determining the acceptance limits for cleaning validation.

Acceptance limits for pharmaceutical manufacturing operation.

1. Approach 1 (Dose criterion):

Not more than 0.001 of minimum daily dose of any product will appear in the maximum daily dose of another product.

Milligrams of active ingredient = $I \times K \times M$ in product A permitted per $J \times L \times 4 \text{ inch}^2$ swab area

$I = 0.001$ of the smallest strength of product A manufactured per day expressed as mg/day and based on the number of milligrams of active ingredient.

$J =$ Maximum number of dosage units of product B per day

$K =$ Number of dosage units per batch of final mixture of product B

$L =$ Equipment surface in common between product A & B expressed as square inches.

$M = 4 \text{ inch}^2/\text{swab}$.

2. Approach 2 (10 ppm criterion)

Any active ingredient can be present in a subsequently manufactured product at a maximum level of 10 ppm. Milligrams of active ingredient = $R \times S \times U$ in product A permitted per $T \times 4 \text{ inch}^2$ swab area

$R = 10\text{mg}$ active ingredient of product A in one kg of product B

$S =$ Number of kilograms per batch of final mixture of product B

$T =$ Equipment surface in common between product A & B expressed as square inches.

$U = 4 \text{ inch}^2/\text{swab}$.

3. Approach 3 (Visually clean criterion)

No quantity of residue should be visible on the equipment after cleaning procedures are performed.

Documentation

Cleaning Validation Protocol is required laying down the procedure on how the cleaning process will be validated. It should include the following:

The objective of the validation process,

Responsibilities for performing and approving the validation study,

Description of the equipment to be used,

The interval between the end of production and the beginning of the cleaning procedures,

Cleaning procedures to be used for each product and each manufacturing system

The number of cleaning cycles to be performed consecutively,

Any routine monitoring requirement,

Sampling procedures, including the rationale for why a certain sampling method is used,

Clearly defined sampling locations,

Data on recovery studies where appropriate,

Analytical methods

The acceptance criteria, including the rationale for setting the specific limits,

The Cleaning Validation Protocol should be formally approved by the plant management, to ensure that aspects relating to the work defined in the protocol, for example personnel resources, are known and accepted by the management. Quality Assurance should be involved in the approval of protocols and reports. The cleaning process should be documented in an SOP.

Standard cleaning procedures: Standard cleaning procedures for each piece of equipment and process should be prepared. It is vital that the equipment

design is evaluated in detail in conjunction with the product residues which are to be removed, the available cleaning agents and cleaning techniques, when determining the optimum cleaning procedure for the equipment.

Cleaning procedures should be sufficiently detailed to remove the possibility of any inconsistencies during the cleaning process. Following parameters are to be considered during cleaning procedures.

A. Equipment Parameters to be evaluated

1. Identification of the equipment to be cleaned
2. 'Difficult to clean' areas
3. Property of materials
4. Ease of disassembly
5. Mobility

B. Residues to be cleaned

1. Cleaning limits
2. Solubility of the residues
3. Length of campaigns

C. Cleaning agent parameters to be evaluated

1. Preferable materials that are normally used in the process
2. Detergents available (as a general guide, minimal use of detergents recommended unless absolutely required)
3. Solubility properties
4. Environmental considerations
5. Health and safety considerations

D. Cleaning techniques to be evaluated

1. Manual cleaning
2. CIP (Clean-in-place)
3. COP (Clean-out-of-place)
4. Semi automatic procedures
5. Automatic procedures
6. Time considerations
7. Number of cleaning cycles

Validation report

A validation report is necessary to present the results and conclusions and secure approval of the study. The report should include the following information:

1. References to all the procedures followed to clean the samples and tests.
2. Physical and analytical test results or references for the same, as well as any pertinent observations.
3. Conclusions regarding the acceptability of the results, and the status of the procedures being validated.
4. Any recommendations based on the results or relevant information obtained during the study including revalidation practices if applicable.
5. Review of any deviations from the protocol.
6. When it is unlikely that further batches of the product will be manufactured for a period, it is

advisable to generate reports on a batch-by-batch basis until such time.

7. The report should conclude an appropriate level of verification subsequent to validation.

REFERENCES :

1. Darshan A. Salade, Kishor S. Arote, P. H. Patil, Pankaj S. Patil, Amol R. Pawar. A Review on Pharmaceutical Cleaning Validation. Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Analysis. 2022; 12(3):197-2.
2. Rajpal G, Arya RKK, Kunwar N. Basic Concept Of Process Validation In Solid Dosage Form (Tablet): A Review. J. Drug Delivery Ther. 2016 ; 6(4):79-87.
3. Ahir KB, Singh KD, Yadav SP, Patel HS, Poyahari CB. Overview of Validation and Basic Concepts of Process Validation. Scholars Academic Journal of Pharmacy 2014;3(2):178-190.
4. Maurya S, Goyal D, Verma C. Cleaning validation in pharmaceutical industry- An overview. Pharmatutor. 2016;4(9):14-20.
5. Asgharian R, Hamedani M, Heydari A. Step by Step How to Do Cleaning Validation. International Journal of Pharmacy and Life Sciences 2014;5(3):3345-3366.
6. Debaje PD, Chhabra GS, Gujarathi N, Jadhav A. Regulatory Aspects of Cleaning and Cleaning Validation in Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients. Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Development. 2018;6(3):69-74.
7. Chandani Y, Rajat V, Anju G. Aspects of Pharmaceutical Process Validation: A Review. International Journal of pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Research. 2018;14(1):55-66.
8. Sharma S, Khurana G, Gupta R. A Review on Pharmaceutical Validation and Its Implications. International journal of Pharmaceutical and Biological Research. 2013;1(3):100-104.
9. Jindal D, Kaur H, Patil RK, Patil HC. Validation – In pharmaceutical industry: Equipment validation: A brief review. Adesh University Journal of Medical Sciences and Research. 2020;2(2):94-98.
10. Kumar V., Sanjeev T, Sharma PK. Overview of cleaning validation in pharmaceutical manufacturing unit Kumar. International Journal of Advanced Research in Pharmaceutical and Bio Sciences. 2012;2(2):154-164.
11. Lodhi B, Padamwar P, Patel A. Cleaning Validation for the Pharmaceuticals, Biopharmaceuticals, Cosmetic and Neutraceuticals Industries. Journal of Innovations in Pharmaceuticals and Biological Sciences. 2014;1(1):27-38.
12. Raj A. Cleaning Validation in Pharmaceutical Industries. Journal of Atoms and Molecules 2014;4(4):779-783.
13. Narayana Murthy D, Chitra K. A Review Article On Cleaning Validation. International Journal of

Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research. 2013; 4(9):3317–3327.

14. Manu C, Gupta V. Review on cleaning validation in pharmaceutical industry. International Journal of PharmTech Research. 2016;9(3):415–421.

15. Khan F, Khan AS, Rao N. Cleaning Validation in Pharmaceutical Industries. International Journal of Research in Pharmacy and Chemistry. 2020;10(2):205–214.